

Research of the process of tar dispersion during interaction with an organic solvent on microfluidic chips

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The preparation and use of tar in various industries presents several problems, including high corrosive activity, very high viscosity, difficulties in disposal. These problems increase the cost, complexity of tar processing and utilization. One possible solution is dispersion in hydrocarbon solvents, which reduces the overall viscosity of the mixture and prevents tar from sticking to the surfaces of processing vessels, facilitating many processes involved in preparing petroleum residue for processing.

This study involves testing a visual analysis of the hydrocarbon feedstock dispersion process efficiency using tar as an example. This allows us to evaluate both the uniformity and size of the distributed particles, as well as the precipitation during interaction with the solvent. An optical microscope with a fluorescent lamp was used for visual observation. The test section is a microfluidic chip with a wide, tortuous structure to ensure high flow rates and prevent high filtration resistance. The dispersion process involves the combined filtration of a mixture of tar and pentane in proportions of 1/3, 1/5, and 1/8, sequentially changing from less to more solvent, through the test area. During the active phase of the experiment, the precipitation rate and particle size were assessed.

The results show a gradual accumulation of particles at the lowest solvent-to-tar ratio, followed by the formation of asphaltene agglomerates with increasing amounts of pentane, and complete clogging of the channel with precipitated particles. This observation shows the need to pay attention

to the reagent ratio parameter. In addition, a time interval was recorded during which some of the tar agglomerates were picked up by the passing mixture flow and carried out through the microchip's outlet. This phenomenon can be useful for selecting the reagent ratio that will ensure cleaning of surfaces contacting with the tar.

The presented technology for conducting a tar dispersion experiment on a microfluidic chip allows to detect asphaltene particles at the micro level, thereby allowing for precise and rapid adjustment of mixture parameters to achieve maximum process efficiency.